

GAMES AS THE STRATEGY IN TEACHING SPEAKING FOR YOUNG LEARNERS

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ABSTRACT

Games are a valuable activity for language learning, especially for young learners. Children enjoy games and thus participate without anxiety. Using Games can create significant change in teaching and learning practice. It is an attractive way to stimulate the student to improve their speaking skill. Games are mostly inclusive activities in that they involve all the children and they can cater to different learning styles and different personalities. The aims of this paper were to introduce games as the strategy in teaching speaking for young learners. An alternative strategy for the teacher to gains young learners attention in learning English. Games also particularly valuable for a child beginning to learn a foreign language. The advantage of using it for student, they can learn how to speak the foreign language while paying games. Using games lead student to study in a fun way and the aspect of meaningful learning achieved. Antonaros and Couri (2003:6) explain that games in foreign language classroom encourage and develop socialization, cooperating with others, learning self-discipline, respecting rules, peer teaching and cooperative learning. Ersoz (2000) also states that games are highly motivating because they are amusing and interesting. They can be used to give practice in all language skills and be used to practice many types of communication.

Keywords: Games, Speaking, Young Learner

INTRODUCTION

Some English teachers see language games as time consumers or classroom techniques for fun, games have a special role in any foreign language teaching program because they facilitate foreign language learning especially for young learners. With the introduction of communicative language teaching, English language teaching and learning has become much more demanding for teachers and learners just like any other innovation poses challenges for its users.

One of the alternative strategy that can be used by the teacher is games because using games become crucially important for English language learners and teachers not only because they provide enjoyment and relaxation, but also as they encourage students to use their language in a creative and communicative manner. Language learning is a challenging task requiring constant effort

especially for young learners. Games encourage learners to direct their energy towards language learning by providing them with meaningful contexts (Wright, Betteridge and Buckby, 1984).

Teachers should not see games as time fillers or tools designed for fun only, but integrate them into their foreign language-teaching program. It is possible to come up with many descriptions proposed by various researchers about the nature of games. Rixon (1991:3), for example, describes games as "form of play governed by rules." Likewise, Hadfield (1990; Quoted in Deesri, 2002:1) describes games as "an activity with rules, a goal and an element of fun." According to Haycraft (1978:94), "Games are an agreeable way of getting a class to use its initiative in English." However, Gibbs (1978; Quoted in Rixon, 1991:3) also mention, as "games are activities carried out by cooperating or competing decision makers, seeking to achieve, within a set of rules, their objectives." The fact that games are the most suitable instructional activities for young learners is obvious because they are a natural part of their existence.

Nedomová (2007:17) argues "young learners are not able to pay their attention for more than 10-20 minutes and after that they start to be bored and tired. Teachers know that young learners like being physically active as they learn by doing. Moreover, they are imaginative and creative and they learn without being aware of it. Besides, young learners use their previous experience, knowledge, several skills, and abilities which help the teacher present the new information by enabling children to practice the new knowledge on top of their previous knowledge (Nedomová, 2007:28).

Bekiri (2003:1) states that when a lesson includes a game, the game gives a chance to the teacher to help learners acquire new forms and lexis in an effective way. It should not be a complicated game, but a simple one because it is usually more effective as young learners find it difficult to understand a long list of rules. Similarly, games should also include praise and encouragement because young learners always love to be the Centre of attention. In addition to all these, it should be born in mind that games should be as short as possible because as mentioned

before, young learners are able to pay their attention to the games just for a limited time.

This paper discuss about the use of games as the strategy in teaching speaking for young learners, games viewed as one of the suitable strategy in giving the best speaking lesson for young learners. Using the games will change the learning process which teacher oriented with conventional strategy to the student oriented to improve the speaking skills of young learners. Some previous studies describe the use of games as the strategy gave a significant impact in English learning especially speaking skill. The paper discussions consist of teaching speaking using games as the strategy, why using games, when and how to use games, and type of language games that can be used by the young learners English teacher.

TEACHING SPEAKING FOR YOUNG LEARNERS

Teaching today has changed a lot over the past years. Once it was all about learners being passive and listening in the classroom, but today learners are usually much more active in the classroom, and what better way to be active than by playing games (Steve Sugar.1998: 3). The national curriculum in foreign languages in Indonesia talks about the importance of keeping teaching methods diverse in order to light and sustain interest amongst students. Teachers can help sustain diversity in a variety of ways, for example by using activities that require students to be creative in thinking and by emphasizing individual learning and cooperative learning equally.

A more specific way that teachers can use in order to keep diversity within the classroom is to not be afraid of using games as a teaching strategy along with other conventional strategy. According to the national curriculum, games can be a good teaching strategy, such as role-playing games, imitation games, theatrical expression and problem solving activities are especially fitting for all stages of language learning. Howard Gardner, who theories that humans have eight intelligences, claims that when exploring a certain topic in school it can, and

should, be approached in 6 different ways in order to maximize the chances of reaching all students in the classroom

According to Slatterly and Willis (2003:4) state that young learners (YL) were 7-12 years old. In Indonesia, we can see that the age of 7-12 years old is the Elementary/primary School. It is widely believed that learning the foreign language in early age will build more proficient speakers of English. When the young learners still in their golden age, learning a foreign language will be easier for them. Especially when the young learners parent active in using English in their daily activity. The activity that created by their parent will stimulate them in acquiring the foreign language. Based of some research also shown that the imitative aspect in learning something for young learners take a significant role in guiding their understanding about speaking using English.

Teaching English for young learner especially speaking skill, need an extra attention. The young learner needs to know that they are learning a foreign language. In teaching the young learner, teacher needs to create multi-strategy in order to propose the best learning experience for the children. Young learners are different with the adult learner, young learners cannot do the same activity again and again, and that will lead the children to the boredom. Harmer (2007:38) stated that children would learn better if the lessons focus on interaction, meaning, and fluency rather than on accuracy. Another suggestion from Brown (2001:89) mention that children need to have all five senses stimulated which can be accomplished by providing sensory aids and physical activity, such role-play, games or total physical response activities.

Speaking skill for young learner is very crucial. As we know the first thing that the children can do is imitating his/her mom voice. And they learn about how to call his mom appropriately. The first acquiring lesson that the children got is his mum/dad name even they never notice the meaning for the first time. Teaching English for children have to consider the foreign language as their tool in communication; the children need to be fluent in using English. And the fact the happen in Indonesia as stated by Damayanti (2010) while teacher provide students

speaking activities, the student do not respond or are not willing to participate actively since there are not enough support for them to speak.

The mastery of speaking skills in early age is a priority for many second-language or foreign-language learners. Therefore, it needs appropriate strategy in teaching speaking. English teachers have responsibility, as they are demanded to have teaching strategy in order to solve the problem faced by the students in learning English. The ability to speak fluently presupposes not only knowledge of language features, but also the ability to process information and language. The goal of teaching speaking skill is to communicate efficiently. Learners should be able to make them understood, using their current proficiency to the fullest.

They should try to avoid confusing in the message due to faulty pronunciation, grammar, or vocabulary, and to observe the social and cultural rules that apply in each communication situation (Burnkart 1998: 2). Thornbury (2007) stated that, "Sometimes experienced teachers developed established routines or expectations that can lead to rude awakenings in the classroom with a new class of students. Teaching speaking means giving the opportunity of students to study about how to combine their ideas and thoughts. Moreover, it is also about how students selecting the words and sentences orally which appropriate to their social setting. Teaching speaking is the way for students to make an interaction to another person in any situation

Young learner and English speaking skill is a new challenge for the children. Concerning their understanding of the foreign language, one of the best and suitable strategies to teach speaking for young learner is using games. Games will create a fun activity to the student and make them enjoy their speaking class. Playing while learning or learning by playing, that make the children interest in making the interaction while using games as the strategy in learning speaking skill. Using games for the young learner give them stimulation in gaining new information or knowledge about English especially speaking skill.

WHY GAMES?

There are some reasons in using games as strategy in teaching speaking for young learners. First, Games add interest to what students might not find very interesting. Sustaining interest can mean sustaining effort (Thiagarajan, 1999; Wright, Betteridge, & Buckby, 2005). Games can help activate students who may have been inactive before, due to lack of interest. Keeping students active is vital because teachers will never be able to actually teach students anything unless they can get them to participate in their own learning process. After all, learning a language involves long-term effort. After attract the young learners attention in playing games while learning, the learning process is half way to achieve the student curiosity in learning the lesson.

Second, Games provide a context for meaningful communication. Even if the game involves discrete language items, such as a spelling game, meaningful communication takes place as students seek to understand how to play the game and as they communicate about the game: before, during, and after the game (Wright, Betteridge, & Buckby, 2005). Games also play a big part in helping participants build relationships, and to feel equal. Playing games in the classroom can also help create a friendly and positive atmosphere where seat arrangement can differ from game to game, and thus cause diversity from the norm which can be extremely helpful in keeping an exciting learning environment. Meaningful communication leads the student to get a great learning experience.

Third, Games can involve all the basic language skills, i.e., listening, speaking, reading, and writing, and a number of skills are often involved in the same game (Lee, 1995). The reason most people want to learn a language is to be able to use it in real situations, for example when visiting foreign country. Games can be a very good way to practice this skill because they can easily be used to reenact various situations from real life and provide students with practice in their fluency. Also, by using games in the classroom the teacher is giving his students a bigger role, and he himself is stepping out of the frontline, which is a positive thing because it allows students to take on more responsibility.

Games are particularly valuable for a child beginning to learn a foreign language. Children just beginning to learn a new language need some time to adapt to the language, its sounds and rhythms. They need exposure to input before they experiment with producing language. Some children will gladly experiment with production but some can be shy and require more time. This 'silent' time/period should be offered to the children and they should never be pressured into producing language. Games, therefore, offer an important tool, which allows children to listen to and comprehend language without requiring production. They can participate fully in all the activities without being pressured to produce language.

The use of games in teaching speaking also creates groups for the young learners to develop their skills in working together with others. The advantages of games played in a groups are, first the team aspect of many games can encourage cooperation and build team spirit (Ersoz, 2000). Second, although many games involve competition, this is not necessarily the case (Orlick, 2006). Third, In most games, everyone has a turn, encouraging everyone to take a turn, rather than letting others do all the talking and other actions, and discouraging one or two people from shutting out others. Gardner (1999) explains that games can connect to variety of intelligences.

Another reason to use games in language learning because many children do not get enough opportunity to play during their free time, which can be traced to the rapid changes in our society. Cities are getting bigger and traffic is getting heavier which means that more and more parents are hesitant to let their children play outside. Also passive activities such as watching television, or the computer screen are seen as being more exciting than actually physically playing, so today the sight of children playing various games in groups outside is becoming much more rare than it was 10, 15 or 20 years ago. This is not a good development, and it can have several bad consequences for our society.

WHEN AND HOW TO USE GAMES?

Games started with the aim of having fun, they can sometimes end badly, for example if someone gets carried away with all the fun and says or does something that hurts someone else or his feelings. When games are used in the language learning the teacher must keep this in mind and control the game in the right way. Also he or she must make sure that every participant has a positive experience because the classroom must not become a place where students feel vulnerable or picked on in. Another thing that is important to acknowledge is the fact that not all games fit the classroom environment, or all groups of students, and that it can be hard finding the right game.

Teachers need to keep in mind is to choose wisely when it comes to selecting a game to use in the classroom because; although one game might be perfect for one teacher or a particular group of students it can be terrible for another teacher or group of students (Ingvar Sigurgeirsson.1995: 3). First of all, the teacher has to look at the group that will be participating in the game and he or she then has to set out a goal for the group, which the game should aim towards (Alanna Jones. 1998: 14). Selecting an appropriate game for specific group of students who are working towards a specific goal can be tricky because, for example, they need to make sure that the game is relevant to the subject, that it fits their students' age and, teachers must remember not to select a game that is too complicated because that might result in a loss of interest amongst the students, or even defeat.

Teachers must make sure they explain the clear instruction about the game in detail before starting the game. During the game it is important for the teachers to observe and be ready to help, but without unnecessarily interrupting the flow of the game because that might affect the fluency, which could result in discouraging students from participating. After the game, it is a good idea to have some sort of a follow up activity planned because it gives the student's time to reflect upon the game and how it turned out (Langran& Purcell.1994: 15-19). It is important for teachers to know that augmenting a game is allowed and can certainly be necessary in some cases. More difficult games can be made easier so they become

a challenge instead of to hard for less skilled or younger students and vice versa (Hadfield.1990: 5).

Games can usually be modified to suit students of various ages; there are certain characteristics in games that appeal to children within specific age groups. For children age 6- 8 repetition is very common in games, rules are often few, and the games usually do not take a very long time. When it comes to children age 9- 11 they have patience for longer games, which often include much more suspense. Also when children reach this age they start to be able to augment the games themselves, for example to bend the rules to make the game more suited for their group. For children older than 12 games are often much more planned and they often emphasize teams and teamwork.

Games can play a range of roles in the language curriculum. Traditionally, games have been used in the language class as warm-ups at the beginning of class, fill-ins when there is extra time near the end of class, or as an occasional bit of spice stirred into the curriculum to add variety. All these are fine, but games can also constitute a more substantial part of language courses (Lee, 1979; Rixon, 1981, Uberman, 1998). In the Presentation-Practice-Production framework (Mauer, 1997), (in which language items are first *presented* for students to listen to and/or read, then *practiced* in a manner in which the language used is controlled, e.g., students read out a dialogue from the textbook in which the two characters compare study habits, and then *produced* by students in a less controlled manner, e.g., two students discuss their own study habits), the games can be either for practicing specific language items or skills or for more communicative language production. Similarly, games can also be used as a way to revise and recycle previously taught language (Uberman, 1998).

Children often are very enthusiastic about games, but precisely for that reason, some older students may worry that games are too childish for them. Teachers need to explain the purpose of the game in order to reassure such students that there is such a phenomenon as "serious fun." Also, older students can be involved in modifying and even creating games. Furthermore, adults have long participated in games on radio and television, not to mention the fact that

popular board games, such as Monopoly, are played by adults. As with other learning activities, teachers need to pay careful attention to the difficulty level of games. Part of the appeal of games lies in the challenge, but if the challenge is too great, some students may become discouraged. The challenge can be of two kinds: understanding how to play the game and understanding the language content. Some suggestions for promoting both types are understanding are:

1. Demonstrations of how the game is played. The teacher can demonstrate with a group of students or a group can demonstrate for the class.
2. A kind of script of what people said as they played or a list of useful phrases. Similarly, key vocabulary and concepts may need to be explained.
3. Clear directions. Demonstrations can accompany directions, and directions can be given when needed, rather than explaining all the steps and rules in one go. Also, some student-initiated modifications can be accepted.
4. Games already known to students.
5. Games used to revise and recycle previously studied content, rather than involving new content.
6. Groups are heterogeneous in terms of current language proficiency, so that the more proficient members can help others.
7. Resources, online or print, such as dictionaries and textbooks.

TYPES OF LANGUAGE GAMES

Classifying games into categories can be difficult, because categories often overlap. Hadfield (1999) explains two ways of classifying language games. First, she divides language games into two types: linguistic games and communicative games. Linguistic games focus on accuracy, such as supplying the correct antonym. On the other hand, communicative games focus on successful exchange of information and ideas, such as two people identifying the differences between their two pictures, which are similar to one another but not exactly alike. Correct language usage, though still important, is secondary to achieving the communicative goal. The second taxonomy that Hadfield uses to classify language games has many more categories. As with the classification of games as linguistic

games or communicative games, some games will contain elements of more than one type.

1. Sorting, ordering, or arranging games. For example, students have a set of cards with different products on them, and they sort the cards into products found at a grocery store and products found at a department store.
2. Information gap games. In such games, one or more people have information that other people need to complete a task. For instance, one person might have a drawing and their partner needs to create a similar drawing by listening to the information given by the person with the drawing. Information gap games can involve a one-way information gap, such as the drawing game just described, or a two-way information gap, in which each person has unique information, such as in a Spot-the-Difference task, where each person has a slightly different picture, and the task is to identify the differences.
3. Guessing games. These are a variation on information gap games. One of the best-known examples of a guessing game is 20 Questions. In which one person thinks of a famous person, place, or thing. The other participants can ask 20 Yes/No questions to find clues in order to guess who or what the person is thinking of.
4. Search games. These games are yet another variant on two-way information gap games, with everyone giving and seeking information. Find Someone Who is a well-known example. Students are given a grid. The task is to fill in all the cells in the grid with the name of a classmate who fits that cell, e.g., someone who is a vegetarian. Students circulate; asking and answering questions to complete their own grid and help classmates complete theirs.
5. Matching games. As the name implies, participants need to find a match for a word, picture, or card. For example, students place 30 word cards; composed of 15 pairs, face down in random order. Each person turns over two cards at a time, with the goal of turning over a matching pair, by using their memory. This is also known as the Pelmanism principle, after Christopher Louis Pelman, a British psychologist of the first half of the 20th century.
6. Labeling games. These are a form of matching, in that participants match labels and pictures.

7. Exchanging games. In these games, students barter cards, other objects, or ideas. Similar are exchanging and collecting games. Many card games fall into this category, such as the children's card game Go Fish
8. Board games. Scrabble is one of the most popular board games that specifically highlight language.
9. Role-play games. The terms *role-play*; *drama*, and *simulation* are sometimes used interchangeably but can be differentiated (Kodotchigova, 2002). Role play can involve students playing roles that they do not play in real life, such as dentist, while simulations can involve students performing roles that they already play in real life or might be likely to play, such as customer at a restaurant. Dramas are normally scripted performances, whereas in role plays and simulations, students come up with their own words, although preparation is often useful.

Another distinction among games is that between competitive games and cooperative ones (Jacobs, in preparation). Research suggests that learning, as well as affective variables, are enhanced by a cooperative environment (Johnson, Johnson, & Stanne; Slavin, 1995). Millis (2005) outlines a number of advantages of cooperative games, such as appropriate anxiety levels and more constructive feedback. Choosing the games type also become the most crucial part for the teachers to propose best speaking class for the student.

CONCLUSION

Based on all of the explanation above it seems clear that games can and should be used as a teaching strategy for speaking class. One reason why games could work well as a teaching strategy is because of the change that has occurred in teaching. where students have been becoming much more active in the whole learning process. Besides giving students a chance to be more active, games usually place the teacher in a background role, and therefore allow the students to take on more responsibility. It has also been made clear that games help create diversity and that can be very helpful in sustaining interest amongst students in the school. Games can also be used to help recreate various situations from real life

and therefore make the learning more real and give the students a sense of what they are doing is relevant. Another benefit to using games in the classroom is that children do mature through games and through playing games they learn many of society's rules and regulations. In addition when using physical games, children would get a change to get a necessary work out that is often lacking today, due to rapid change in our society.

Teacher needs to keep in mind that not all games fit certain students and some cannot be played inside the classroom. When selecting a game teachers need to ask themselves, "What are the goals am I trying to achieve by playing this game?" and they have to make sure that the game they choose is not too easy but at the same time not too difficult. If teachers believe a certain game might be too difficult for their students they need to be aware that they need to augment the game to make it more fitting. Finally, teachers need to make sure they explain all rules in detail, that during the game they do not interrupt the flow of the game and to plan some sort of a follow-up activity after the game. Games can be very beneficial in language teaching. Using games as the strategy propose the great learning experience for young learner in learning English especially speaking skills.

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